

Studies in Pyrazolone-Azo Dyes. Part II : Synthesis of Some 1-Anilinomalonyl-3-Methyl-4-Substituted Phenyl-Azo-5-Pyrazolones*

V. S. JOLLY, A. K. SHRIVASTAVA, S. P. SINGH and K. S. TIWARI

Department of Chemistry, Maharaja College, Chhatarpur-471 001

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Synthesis of some 1-anilinomalonyl-3-methyl-4-substituted phenyl-azo-5-pyrazolones is reported. Ethylacetoacetate on condensing with diazotised amines gave ethyl- α -substituted phenyl-azo-acetoacetates which on treatment with acid hydrazides of malonanilic acid series, in acetic acid, gave pyrazolone-azo dyes. These dyes impart mostly yellow colour to cotton, silk, wool and polyester fibres. None of the products show significant bacteriostatic or fungicidal activity.

IN view of anticancerous, fungicidal and bacteriostatic activities of pyrazolone derivatives¹⁻⁴ and of malonanilic acid hydrazides⁵ and profiting by the earlier work of Jolly and co-workers⁶ we undertook the synthesis of some new pyrazolone-azo dyes having anilinomalonic acid moiety.

The experimental conditions leading to these dyes comprised condensation of ethylacetoacetate with diazotised aromatic amines affording ethyl- α -(substituted) phenyl-azo-acetoacetates. The later on heating with acid hydrazides of malonanilic acid series furnished pyrazolone-azo-dyes of the type I.

Data concerning the dyes are set out in the Table 1. Most of the dyes are yellow in colour and possess high melting point. The IR spectra of the pyrazolone-azo-dyes showed the presence of N=N, C=N and C=O bonds as sharp and strong peaks in the region, 1570-1540 cm⁻¹, 1600-1585 cm⁻¹ and 1675-1660 cm⁻¹ respectively. Some of the dyes (Sl. No. 1, 4, 6, 10, 14,

17, 18, 20, 24, 25, 28, 31, 33 and 35, Table 1), have been examined for their dyeing characteristics on cotton, silk, wool and polyester fibres. These dyes produced mostly yellow shades on these fibres.

Biological activity : The compounds (Sl. No. 1, 14, 17, 28, 31 and 33, Table 1) have been tested for antimicrobial activity against *S. typhi*, *E. coli*, *C. albicans*, *C. neoformelus*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis* and *A. mgei*, at concentration 100 μ g/ml. All of them were found to be ineffective.

Experimental

Ethyl- α -(substituted) phenyl-azo-acetoacetate⁴ and malonanilic acid hydrazides⁵ were prepared by the methods reported in the literature.

Preparation of 1-anilino-malonyl-3-methyl-4-p-methyl-phenyl-azo-5-pyrazolone :

Ethyl- α -p-methyl phenyl-azo-acetoacetate (0.49 g) and malonanilic acid hydrazide (0.38 g) were dissolved in acetic acid (6.5 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for three hours. Solution was concentrated and cooled in ice when the dye separated. It was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous acetic acid. Yield, 0.40 g (53.3%), m. p. 280°. IR(KBr) :

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S. No.	R'	Colour	m. p. °C R=CH ₃	Mol. formula	N%	
					Found	Calc.
1.	H	Y	280	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₅	18.74	18.56
2.	CH ₃ ^o (o)	LY	291	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₅	18.01	17.90
3.	CH ₃ (m)	LY	294	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₅	18.06	17.90
4.	CH ₃ (p)	DY	299	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₅	17.79	17.90
5.	Cl (o)	Y	295	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₅ Cl	17.23	17.01
6.	Cl (m)	BY	>300	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₅ Cl	17.40	17.01
7.	Cl (p)	BY	308	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₅ Cl	17.41	17.01
8.	OCH ₃ (o)	Y	293	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₅	17.22	17.19
9.	OCH ₃ (m)	Y	297	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₅	17.30	17.19
10.	OCH ₃ (p)	BY	302	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₅	17.28	17.19
			R=COOH			
11.	H	Y	296	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₅	17.16	17.19
12.	CH ₃ (o)	BY	308	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅	16.46	16.62
13.	CH ₃ (m)	DY	>300	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅	16.45	16.62
14.	CH ₃ (p)	Y	301	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅	16.80	16.62
15.	Cl (o)	Y	286	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₅ Cl	15.92	15.85
16.	Cl (m)	Y	298	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₅ Cl	15.88	15.85
17.	Cl (p)	BY	290	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₅ Cl	15.86	15.85
18.	OCH ₃ (o)	BY	287	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₅	16.18	16.23
19.	OCH ₃ ^o (m)	Y	>300	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₅	16.16	16.23
20.	OCH ₃ (p)	BY	306	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₅	16.24	16.23
21.	OC ₂ H ₅ (o)	Y	284	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₅	15.48	15.52
22.	OC ₂ H ₅ (p)	Y	292	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₅	15.46	15.52
23.	COOH(o)	BY	302	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₇ N ₅	15.58	15.50
24.	COOH(p)	BY	312	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₇ N ₅	15.54	15.50
			R=NO ₂			
25.	H	DY	266	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₆	20.46	20.58
26.	CH ₃ ^o (o)	DY	262	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₆	19.80	19.90
27.	CH ₃ (m)	BY	268	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₆	19.87	19.90
28.	CH ₃ (p)	DY	251	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₆	19.75	19.90
29.	Cl (o)	DY	265	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₆ Cl	18.79	19.00
30.	Cl (m)	Y	228	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₆ Cl	19.08	19.00
31.	Cl (p)	DY	255	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₆ Cl	19.10	19.00
32.	OCH ₃ (m)	DY	264	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₆	19.10	19.13
33.	OCH ₃ (p)	Y	253	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₆	19.11	19.13
34.	OC ₂ H ₅ (o)	LY	271	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₆	18.60	18.58
35.	OC ₂ H ₅ (p)	Y	260	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₆	18.63	18.58
36.	C ₂ H ₅ (o)	DY	275	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₆	18.57	18.42

BY=Bright Yellow, DY=Deep Yellow, LY=Light Yellow, Y=Yellow.

1565 cm^{-1} (N=N), 1595 cm^{-1} (C=N) and 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O). Found : N, 18.74 ; $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N}_5$ requires N, 18.56%.

The aforementioned procedure is illustrative of the method used in the preparation of the dyes listed in the Table 1.

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References

1. W. WILSON and N. BOTTIGLIERI, *Cancer chemotherapy*, 1962, 21, 137.
2. G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 351.
3. P. S. FERNANDES, B. SANDHYA, G. PHILIP and V.V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 830.
4. K. SHRIVASTAVA and J. K. MAHROTRA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, 32, 116.
5. B. S. RATHORE and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 591.
6. V. S. JOLLY, unpublished work.